

The role of body appreciation and boredom on married men's sexual satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

Adult male appreciation of his body can affect sexual satisfaction. In addition, boredom caused by a lack of variety in sexual relations can also have an impact on sexual satisfaction in marriage. The aim of this study was to examine the role of body appreciation in predicting increased sexual satisfaction, either directly or indirectly through the mediation of sexual boredom, in early and middle-aged married men. Data were collected from a total of 382 participants (mean age 38 years) using a cross-sectional survey method with convenience sampling. Participants completed the extended satisfaction with life scale (ESWLS), body appreciation scale-2 (BAS-2), and sexual boredom scale (SBS). The results showed that sexual boredom partially mediated the indirect role of body appreciation in predicting sexual satisfaction ($B=0.159$; $z=4.383$; $sig.=0.001<0.05$) because body appreciation can also directly predict increased sexual satisfaction ($B=0.814$, $t=11.418$; $sig.=0.001<0.05$). This result indicates that body appreciation as an internal factor plays a greater role in predicting high sexual satisfaction in early and middle adulthood men.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sexual activity is basically a normal activity in a marital relationship. One of the crucial factors in sexuality is sexual satisfaction, which can be defined as a subjective evaluation, whether positive or negative, related to the sexual intercourse that takes place [1]. The higher the level of sexual satisfaction of an individual, the more positive impact it will have on emotional closeness, communication intimacy, and satisfaction in the relationship with the partner [2]. Men who have partners are likely to have sexual satisfaction scores 2 to 7.5 times higher than men without partners [3]. According to data from the Central Bureau of Statistics in 2021, the average age of first marriage for men in Indonesia is most commonly between 22 to 24 years old (34.96%), and the second most common age group is between 25 to 30 years old (32.13%) [4]. Based on this data, it can be said that the average age of first marriage for men is in the early adulthood stage. However, marital life continues into the middle adulthood stage, although sexual activity tends to decrease and occur less frequently compared to early adulthood [5]. Therefore, this study was conducted on male respondents in the early and middle adulthood stages.

Several factors can affect sexual satisfaction, including body image, gender, body mass index, frequency of sexual activity, commitment in the relationship, length of the relationship, and relationship satisfaction [6]–[8]. Body image is one of the crucial factors in an individual's sexual satisfaction [6], [8]. Body image can be formed from a person's sexual experiences, and vice versa. Worrying about what others

think of one's body can make an individual feel tense and passive during sexual activity, resulting in disrupted sexual satisfaction [8].

Body image can be distinguished as negative and positive body image [9]. Positive body image should not be portrayed as a low-level negative body image. Positive body image is a multifaceted concept, such as body appreciation, body image flexibility, body functional orientation, and body functional satisfaction, which encompass much more than body satisfaction or aesthetic evaluation [10]. Individuals can have a positive body image when they begin to accept and appreciate their body appearance, regardless of body shape and size, and appreciate the function and health of the body instead of only focusing on appearance [11]. Research in Norway with female and male respondents aged 18 to 29 years showed that dissatisfaction with the body and a focus on appearance can lead to avoidance of sexual relationships, thus automatically hindering desire, satisfaction, and sexual performance. Also, men were more likely to have a positive body image, thus increasing the likelihood of sexual satisfaction [8].

One important construct of positive body image is body appreciation. Body appreciation is a construct that encompasses different components beyond just satisfaction/dissatisfaction, including respect and protection of the body, having positive opinions about the body, accepting the body regardless of its shape/size, and explicit rejection of media-promoted beauty ideals as the only form of human attractiveness [12]. People who appreciate, accept, and respect their bodies are less likely to be dissatisfied with their bodies, want to change their appearance, be influenced by external pressures related to body ideals, and engage in disordered eating because they are better able to conceptualize their bodies holistically while also possessing the necessary skills to refrain from focusing on their outer appearance or perceived bodily imperfections [13]. Body appreciation in 18 year old males was not related to the drive for thinness, media influence, or appearance pressures perceived from romantic partners/friends [14]. Previous research has shown a relationship between body image in general and sexual satisfaction in adult men and women [7], [8], [15]. A considerable amount of literature has found a correlation between negative body image and sexual satisfaction specifically in adult women [1], [16]–[18]. Therefore, in this study, the researcher aims to examine the direct role of one dimension of positive body image, namely body appreciation, on sexual satisfaction in early and middle adulthood men.

In addition to understanding the role of positive body image in sexual satisfaction, boredom may also be an important factor to consider in marital life. Sexual boredom has a significant negative correlation with overall life satisfaction as well as sexual satisfaction [19]. A systematic review of sexual boredom found that it was negatively correlated with sexual responses like sexual arousal, sexual desire, orgasm, sexual satisfaction, and relationship satisfaction, but positively correlated with dyadic sexual discord and infidelity, implying that more research is needed to help couples who are experiencing sexual boredom [20]. Research comparing male and female sexual boredom found that male participants experienced more sexual boredom and reported higher levels of sexual boredom compared to female participants [20], [21]. Basically, sexual boredom can be triggered by prolonged mismatch between desired expectations (for fulfilling needs) and actual experiences. In a qualitative study of 12 men, sexual boredom was identified as an emotion defined by indifference or demotivation toward sexual partners or sexual connections, which would eventually emerge in long-term exclusive sexual relationships if partners did not manage it appropriately [22]. On the other hand, it has been proposed that sexual boredom serves an adaptive role by reminding individuals to take action. Sexual boredom is a relationship difficulty that does not include many partner flaws. Indeed, some people identify boredom with their partner's features (e.g., unattractive partner, bothersome partner), but the causes that frequently arise are relationship dynamics (e.g., doing the same thing, routine, lack of communication) [23].

Previous studies on the relationship between sexual boredom, sexual satisfaction, and sex life have been extensively conducted [19]–[23]. However, research linking body image, specifically positive body image, and sexual boredom with sexual satisfaction is still very limited. There has been no specific research on sexual boredom or research linking body appreciation, sexual boredom, and sexual satisfaction in the Indonesian literature. Furthermore, sex research in Indonesia is still deemed sensitive, so its dissemination is still restricted. Therefore, we were interested in examining the indirect role of body appreciation in predicting increased sexual satisfaction in early and middle-aged married men in Indonesia, with sexual boredom as a mediator. The proposed hypotheses were:

H1: Body appreciation plays a direct role in predicting increased sexual satisfaction in early and middle adulthood married men.

H2: Body appreciation plays an indirect role in predicting increased sexual satisfaction in early and middle adulthood married men with sexual boredom as a mediator.

Based on the description above, the role of body appreciation in sexual satisfaction with sexual boredom as a mediator can be illustrated through the following chart as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Hypothetical model

2. METHOD

This study used a quantitative survey method with a cross-sectional study design on a sample of married early and middle adulthood men ($N_{(20-40 \text{ years})} = 226$, $N_{(41-60 \text{ years})} = 156$; respectively), see Table 1. The size of the sample taken from the population is determined based on calculations using the Raosoft sample size calculator [24]. The calculation used a 5% margin of error, 95% confidence level, an estimated population of 20,000, and a 50% response distribution, so the recommended minimum sample size was 377 participants. The margin of error is the amount of error that can be tolerated. The margin of error will be related to the level of confidence. A lower margin of error and higher confidence level requires a larger sample size. The way to determine the margin of error and level of confidence is to use a normal distribution and also look at the population size. The population estimate was 20,000 because the sample size does not change much for populations over 20,000. We set the response distribution at 50% because this response distribution assumes 50% of the general population answered “Yes” and the remaining 50% answered “No” [24].

Table 1. The characteristics of participants (N=382)

Characteristics	f	%	Characteristics	f	%
Age (Years)			Body mass index (BMI)		
20-27	59	15.4	Underweight	18	4.7
28-35	123	32.2	Normal weight	144	37.7
36-43	68	17.8	Overweight	81	21.2
44-51	82	21.5	Obesity I	107	28
52-60	50	13.1	Obesity II	32	8.4
Marital age (Years)			Weight perception		
0-5	153	40	Underweight	37	9.7
6-11	76	19.9	Normal weight	207	54.2
12-17	49	12.8	Overweight	112	29.3
18-23	56	14.7	Obesity	26	6.8
24-29	33	8.6			
30-35	11	2.9			
36-41	3	.8			
42-48	1	.3			
Domicile					
Java	295	77.2			
Borneo	26	6.8			
Bali	25	6.5			
Sulawesi	16	4.2			
Sumatra	13	3.4			
Papua	7	1.8			

All ethical procedures were followed and after the approval process was completed, permission was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Universitas Surabaya (No: 128/KE/X/2022). Participants were given the opportunity to read the informed consent and ask questions related to the questionnaire. The questionnaire was completed within approximately 15 to 20 minutes. We used open-ended questions to explore demographic data and the characteristics of respondents who were willing to participate, as well as closed-ended questionnaires consisting of Likert scale items for each variable. Sexual satisfaction was measured using the extended satisfaction with life scale (ESWLS), which consists of five favorable items with Likert scale response options ranging from 1 to 7 [25]. Body appreciation was measured using the body appreciation scale-2 (BAS-2), which consists of 10 favorable items with Likert scale response options ranging from 1 to 5 [9]. Sexual boredom was measured using the sexual boredom scale (SBS), which consists of 16 favorable and two unfavorable items with Likert scale response options ranging from 1 to 7 [19]. Each item from each scale has undergone content validation to adapt the translation of the scales, and each item also has high reliability (Cronbach's alpha >0.8 and CITC >0.3). The statistical techniques used to test the hypotheses in this study were parametric Pearson correlation, regression analysis with a mediator, and Sobel

test. The analysis was performed using SPSS software to examine the direct and indirect effects of the predictor variables (X) on the response variable (Y) through the mediator variable (M).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The role of body appreciation in directly predicting the increased sexual satisfaction of early and middle adulthood married men

Before testing the role of body appreciation directly and indirectly on sexual satisfaction, it is important to examine the correlation between variables first. Based on Table 2, it can be seen that there is a significant positive correlation between body appreciation and sexual satisfaction ($r=0.551$, $sig.=0.001<0.01$). Furthermore, sexual boredom and sexual satisfaction also have a significant negative correlation ($r=-0.473$, $sig.=0.001<0.01$). Likewise, body appreciation and sexual boredom also show a significant negative correlation ($r=-0.252$, $sig.=0.001<0.01$). The significant correlation between these three variables supports the use of regression analysis with a mediator.

Based on the results of the test conducted, it can be known that body appreciation can play a direct or indirect role in the increase of sexual satisfaction. Body appreciation has been proven to significantly predict the direct increase in sexual satisfaction ($\beta=0.461$, $B=0.814$, $sig.=0.001<0.05$, $R^2=0.254$) with an effective contribution of 25.4%, show in Table 3 and Figure 2 (path c'). This shows that when adult men have higher body appreciation, their sexual satisfaction tends to increase. This finding is consistent with Cash's theory, that individuals with high body appreciation leads to high sexual experiences and satisfaction [26].

Table 2. Correlation analysis between body appreciation, sexual satisfaction, and sexual boredom

No.	Variable	1	2	3
1	Body appreciation	-		
2	Sexual satisfaction	.551**	-	
3	Sexual boredom	-.252**	-.473**	-

**Correlation is significant at the .01 level (1-tailed).

Table 3. Regression analysis and mediation analysis with SOBEL test of body appreciation on sexual satisfaction with sexual boredom as A mediator

Variabel	R ²	β	B	S.E.	t	Sig.
BA → SB (path a)	.064	-.252	-.437	.086	-5.079	.001
SB → SS.BA (path b)	-.09	-.357	-.363	.041	-8.843	.001
BA → SS.SB (path c')	.254	.461	.814	.071	11.418	.001
BA → SS (path c)	.303	.551	.972	.076	12.857	.001
Variable		Value	S.E. Indirect	t/z	Sig.	
BA → SB → SS		.159	.036	4.383	.001	

Note: BA = Body Appreciation, SS = Sexual Satisfaction, SB = Sexual Boredom

Indirect effect=.159; z =4.383; sig.=.001<.05

Figure 2. Final model

This is also supported by descriptive data results as shown in Table 4, that show that participants' evaluation of their bodies plays a significant role in sexual satisfaction, which can support sexual satisfaction (58.1%) and increase sexual desire (50.5%). Body appreciation leads to comfort, motivation, self-confidence, and sensitivity to body sensations, so individuals can be more open to sexual experiences with their partners to reach the point of satisfaction [27]. Body appreciation is a form of gratitude related to body function, health, and characteristics, by paying more attention, praising, and appreciating the uniqueness of their bodies [26].

Table 4. Description of participant responses regarding sexual satisfaction, body appreciation, and sexual boredom

Participant responses	f	%	Participant responses	f	%
Participants' views regarding sexual life with partners			Partners' views of sexual life		
Warm	262	68.6	Warm	252	65.9
Varied	180	47.1	Varied	185	48.4
Exciting	174	45.6	Exciting	167	43.7
Monotone	39	10.2	Monotone	33	8.6
Boring	18	4.7	Boring	14	3.7
Disappointing	13	3.4	Disappointing	14	3.7
Lack of communication	4	1	Just normal	4	1
Lack of appreciation from partners	3	.8	Do not know	4	1
Just normal	4	1	Others... (not prioritizing sex, lack of communication)	2	.5
Things affecting sexual satisfaction			Effects of body evaluation on sexual satisfaction		
Variation of sexual relations	243	63.6	Supports sexual satisfaction	222	58.1
Frequency of sexual intercourse	227	59.4	Increase sexual desire	193	50.5
Couples orgasm	172	45	Nothing	95	24.9
Partner's body shape	146	38.2	Reduce sexual satisfaction	27	7.1
Self orgasm	134	35.1	Reduce sexual desire	21	5.5
Self-body shape	134	35.1	Sexual dissatisfaction and no sexual desire	3	.8
Duration of sexual intercourse	107	28	Increase self-confidence	3	.8
Communication	16	4.2	Reduce self-confidence	1	.3
Couple mood	6	1.6	Most liked body part		
Appreciation from partner	6	1.6	Face (facial shape and skin color)	192	50.3
Foreplay/warm-up	5	1.3	Overall appearance	152	39.8
The right time to have sex	5	1.3	Hair	148	38.7
Others... (Self-confidence, intimacy together, physical condition)	8	2.1	Upper body (example: chest, shoulders, arms)	144	37.7
Participant's feelings about their body			Height	96	25.1
Affectionate	234	61.3	Weight	69	18.1
Satisfied	178	46.6	Muscle shape	57	14.9
Proud	152	39.8	Midsection (example: waist, abdomen)	50	13.1
Embarrassed	19	5	Lower body (example: hips, buttocks, thighs, calves)	45	11.8
Self-confident	11	2.9	None	18	4.7
Lack of confidence	8	2.1	Efforts made to overcome boredom in sexual relations with partners		
Disappointed	6	1.6	Create a romantic atmosphere	280	73.3
Grateful	6	1.6	Engage in sexual relationships in a different setting than usual (hotels and out of town)	249	65.2
Other... (Hate it, make certain efforts to improve, so-so)	7	1.8	Sending "seductive" (sexually charged) messages/pictures	88	23
Feeling bored in sexual relations			Watch porn videos	66	17.3
No	267	69.9	Communication with partners (mutual trust building, mutual openness, mutual appreciation)	21	5.5
Yes	115	30.1	Trying to explore a variety of sexual style positions	14	3.7
Causes of boredom in sexual relations with partners			Remembering and repeating the first date (honeymoon, spending time together, recreation)	13	3.4
None	231	60.5	None	4	1
Work-related fatigue	124	32.5	Others... (Using sex toys, dawn attack)	4	1
Monotonous sexual relationships	63	16.5			
Feel unsatisfied	33	8.6			
Changes in the body shape of the partner	19	5			
Lack of appreciation from partner	8	2.1			
Lack of communication	8	2.1			
Others... (bad timing, partner's mood, insecure about appearance, not having children)	8	2.1			

Based on median analysis as shown in Table 5, it is known that most participants had a relatively high body appreciation because the median of participants' answers was at 4.30 (approaching the maximum score). These results are also supported by descriptive data as shown in Table 4, that show that most participants feel affectionate (61.3%), satisfied (46.6%), and proud (39.8%) of their bodies. Participants'

sexual satisfaction in median analysis as shown in Table 5, is classified as satisfied (score 6), indicating that high body appreciation is also related to high sexual satisfaction.

Table 5. Median Analysis of Each Variable

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Median
Sexual satisfaction	1	7	6
Sexual boredom	1	7	2.13
Body appreciation	2	5	4.30

This study demonstrated that physical appearance and men's perception of their own bodies were important, not only for women. Men tend to focus on body shape and height [28]. Table 4 shows that male participants preferred certain body parts such as the face (facial shape and skin color), overall appearance, hair, and upper body. As previously theorized, physical components played an important role in supporting sexual activity. Body appreciation is an internal factor that contributes to sexual desire and function in sexual satisfaction [15].

Previous research stated that body appreciation among adult women is often associated with body mass index [16]. The findings of this study also demonstrated that body appreciation among early and middle-aged adult married men is related to body mass index (BMI) and weight perception. Demographic data correlation analysis as shown in Table 6, indicates that BMI ($r=-0.087$, $sig.=0.046<0.05$) and weight perception ($r=-0.099$, $sig.=0.027<0.05$) had a significant negative correlation with sexual satisfaction. These results suggest that higher BMI and/or weight perception of participants led to lower sexual satisfaction. The individual's BMI and weight perception had an impact on their sexual esteem, which affects their sexual satisfaction [15]. Descriptive data in Table 4, show that self-body shape (35.1%) and partner's body shape (38.2%) could influence participants' sexual satisfaction.

Most individuals had a normal BMI (37.7%) and weight perception (54.2%) as shown in Table 1, indicating that individuals' perception of their weight tends to align with their actual BMI. This also indicated a significant positive relationship between BMI and weight perception ($r=0.755$, $sig.=0.001<0.01$) as shown in Table 6. Individuals with high body appreciation tend to focus on their body health by maintaining a normal weight, which leads to an increase in individual sexual satisfaction [12], [14], [29].

Table 6. Demographic data correlation results with sexual satisfaction

Variable	r	Sig.	Description
Age – Sexual Satisfaction	-.029	.288	Not significant
Age of marriage – Sexual satisfaction	-.018	.361	Not significant
Developmental stage – Sexual satisfaction	-.040	.219	Not significant
BMI – Sexual satisfaction	-.087*	.046	Significant
Weight perception – Sexual satisfaction	-.099*	.027	Significant
BMI-Weight perception	.755**	.001	Significant

**Correlation is significant at the .01 level (1-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the .05 level (1-tailed).

3.2. The role of sexual boredom as a mediator between body appreciation and sexual satisfaction in early and middle adulthood married men

Sexual boredom is a failure to maintain attractiveness and comfort in a relationship [30]. There are several conditions that affect this attractiveness, such as fatigue, stress, monotonous sex life, passive partner, excessive masturbation, too many other relationship problems, and poor communication [31]. Most of the aforementioned factors supported the results of this research. Most participants (60.5%) answered that there was nothing specific that caused boredom in their sexual relationship with their partner, but 32.5% of participants felt that work-related fatigue was the biggest cause of sexual boredom and the second was monotonous sexual relationships (16.5%) as shown in Table 4. Some of the open-ended responses from participants were unique, but due to the limitations of quantitative research, researchers focused more on the most common responses. Qualitative research can be used to highlight these unique responses.

Sexual boredom in men tends to be described as boredom of sex caused by repeated unpleasant sexual relationships with their partner, and it has been found to affect men more than women [22]. Sexual boredom is basically related to situations that are less varied, low arousal, and insufficient stimulation [19]. The importance of maintaining intimacy, communication, frequency, and variation in sexual relationships can prevent sexual boredom [19], [22], [32]. These factors also fall under external factors that support

individual sexual satisfaction [15], [33]. These findings are also supported by the results of descriptive data in Table 4, which show that the factors that can affect sexual satisfaction were sexual variety (63.6%), followed by sexual frequency (59.4%). Furthermore, it is important to maintain intimacy and warmth with one's partner [34]. This is supported by the descriptive data results from participants, which suggest that to prevent boredom as shown in Table 4, individuals can create a romantic atmosphere (73.3%) and engage in sexual relationships in a different setting than usual (hotel and out of town) (65.2%).

Based on the descriptive data as shown in Table 4, it is known that the majority of participants (69.9%) did not feel bored in their sexual relationship with their partner. This is also reflected in the median analysis results, see Table 5, where the participants' sexual boredom score was 2.13, indicating a low tendency towards sexual boredom. Individuals with a low level of sexual boredom tend to have high sexual satisfaction and a fulfilling sexual life [31]. In addition to the previous discussion on sexual satisfaction median, it can be seen from Table 4 that the participants' views on their sexual life with their partner were generally warm (68.6%), varied (47.1%), and exciting (45.6%). Their partners' views on their sexual life were also similar, see in Table 4, with warm (65.9%), varied (48.4%), and exciting (43.7%).

However, sexual boredom has been proven to be a partial mediator between body appreciation and sexual satisfaction, it can be seen in Table 3 and Figure 2, because body appreciation had a significant negative influence on sexual boredom ($B=-0.437$, $\text{sig.}=0.001<0.05$), sexual boredom had a significant negative influence on sexual satisfaction ($B=-0.363$, $\text{sig.}=0.001<0.05$), and body appreciation also had a significant direct effect on sexual satisfaction ($B=0.814$, $\text{sig.}=0.001<0.05$). In addition, the results of the mediation analysis using the SOBEL Test show a significant indirect effect between body appreciation and sexual satisfaction with the mediator variable of sexual boredom ($IE=0.159$, $z=4.383$, $\text{sig.}=0.001<0.05$, it can be seen in Table 3 and Figure 2). These results indicates that higher levels of body appreciation predict lower levels of sexual boredom, and subsequently, lower levels of sexual boredom predict higher levels of sexual satisfaction in early and middle adulthood married men. Previous studies have also shown that sexual boredom is significantly negatively related to sexual satisfaction in marriage [30], [31].

The appreciation of one's body and sexual boredom are also related to an individual's sexual motivation and pleasure. When individuals have appreciation for their bodies, they feel more confident, which increases their motivation to engage in sexual activities. As a result, they become more comfortable and willing to explore different variations and other activities to enhance their sexual satisfaction. Conversely, when someone has low sexual motivation, it may lead to sexual boredom because sexual activities involve frequency, intimacy, and variation. Thus, without intimacy, sexual boredom may occur [30], [32], [35]. Therefore, when individuals have a high level of body appreciation, they are less likely to experience sexual boredom, and their sexual satisfaction is more likely to increase.

However, the mediating role of sexual boredom is partial, which means that body appreciation plays a larger role than sexual boredom itself. Indirectly, sexual boredom can be a mediator between body appreciation and sexual satisfaction, but body appreciation itself can directly predict sexual satisfaction. Sexual boredom can basically contain an external factor of the individual, while body appreciation is essentially an internal factor within the individual. The role of body appreciation as an internal factor is more influential in predicting high sexual satisfaction. The presence of internal factors in individuals can have a greater impact on the role of sexual boredom in individual sexual satisfaction [30].

The correlation analysis between demographic data and sexual satisfaction, Table 6 showed that age ($r=-0.029$, $\text{sig.}=0.288>0.05$), developmental stage ($r=-0.040$, $\text{sig.}=0.219>0.05$), and age of marriage ($r=-0.018$, $\text{sig.}=0.361>0.05$) did not have a significant relationship with sexual satisfaction. This finding differs from previous research which found that the longer a relationship (age of marriage and duration of cohabitation) correlates with lower emotional intimacy and sexual satisfaction [31]. According to Alleva *et al.* age is only an idealization in a culture, where at a younger age individuals will experience higher sexual satisfaction, but in reality, this is not accurate [14]. Previous research also stated that body shape perception predicts sexual satisfaction, but assumptions and factors that can influence one's perception of their body will be processed throughout their life journey, and can change depending on the individual, not their age [1].

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussion presented in the previous section, it can be concluded that body appreciation as part of a positive body image plays a significant positive role in predicting sexual satisfaction. The higher an individual's body appreciation, the higher their sexual satisfaction tends to be. Furthermore, it is evident that body mass index (BMI) and perceived weight also negatively correlate with sexual satisfaction. The higher the BMI category and perceived weight, the lower the sexual satisfaction tends to be. BMI and perceived weight are positively correlated with each other.

High levels of sexual boredom can also predict a decrease in sexual satisfaction. Sexual boredom also serves as a partial mediator in the relationship between body appreciation and sexual satisfaction.

Individuals with body appreciation, but with high levels of sexual boredom, are likely to experience lower sexual satisfaction compared to those without sexual boredom. However, because sexual boredom is a partial mediator, body appreciation itself can directly predict sexual satisfaction. The role of internal factors in individuals, such as body appreciation, is more significant. Therefore, body appreciation can directly predict sexual satisfaction. It can also be concluded that there is no significant correlation between age, developmental stages (early and middle adulthood), and age of marriage with sexual satisfaction.

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